

Characteristics of Neogene clay materials in Northwest Bulgaria – new data for the areas near Bela and Staropatitsa villages

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Abstract. Clay materials have a variety of unique characteristics and have various applications in many industries. In this paper, we represent new data about the mineralogical and chemical characteristics of the Neogene clay materials from the areas of the villages of Bela and Staropatitsa, Northwest Bulgaria. The phase composition of the samples mainly consists of quartz and clay minerals, which in both sites are represented by smectite and kaolinite types, with mica, chlorite, illite, and potassium feldspars present. The chemical analysis indicated that silica and alumina were predominant in the analyzed samples, with medium contents of iron oxide. The percentage of MgO, K₂O, and TiO₂ content is explained by the presence of montmorillonite minerals, illite/mica, and anatase. The high values of the Chemical Index of Alteration (CIA) show that the clay materials underwent intense alteration. Further research into the chemical and mineralogical properties and the technical parameters of these clay materials is critical for understanding their formation processes, assessing their industrial applications, and improving the geologic and geotechnical assessments related to environmental implications.

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INTRODUCTION

Clay materials are unique due to their plasticity, high cohesion, water-holding capacity, and wide range of colors. They are easily molded and shaped, provide strength and structural integrity, and are suitable for retaining moisture in the soil. Clays' unique characteristics make them versatile and valuable in various industries. Furthermore, the mineralogical composition of clays can provide valuable information about past environmental conditions. Clays have wide-ranging environmental influence, impacting soil fertility, nutrient cycling, contaminant adsorption, erosion control, and engineering applications,

and understanding their specific characteristics is crucial for sustainable land use, resource management, and mitigating potential negative impacts on ecosystems and human activities.

The clay materials that are the object of this study are situated in the area between the villages of Rakovitsa, Golemanovo, Staropatitsa, and Bela, Northwest Bulgaria. They are located in the Rakevo wedge of the Krivodol Formation, which is Neogene in age (Kojumdgieva and Popov, 1988). Their formation began at the end of the Neogene, with the formation of clayey sand complexes. The structural characteristics of the area suggest the presence of transport channels, such as river valleys, for the

transportation and deposition of the disintegrated and weathered materials of the acidic granitic massive located in the southern margin of an imposed depression. In general, the studied clay materials are light gray in color, with a small amount of sand components, high plasticity, and their characteristics such as mineralogy, chemical composition and rheology in the studied area were not studied in detail. Similar clay materials were studied during the geological mapping in scale 1:100 000 (in the areas of Bela and Rakovitsa) and their industrial application was evaluated as negative.

To examine the mineralogical and chemical characteristics of the studied clay materials, we collected samples from two different localities and performed a mineralogical analysis of the phase composition and chemical analysis for determining the major element concentrations. The obtained results revealed that the analyzed samples consist mainly of quartz and clay minerals, with mica, chlorite, illite, and potassium feldspars. Chemical composition

is represented predominantly by silica and alumina with medium content of iron oxide. The high SiO_2 content indicates quartz prevalence, while kaolinite, goethite, nontronite, and chlorite minerals contribute to Fe_2O_3 concentration. The chemical and mineralogical properties of the studied clay materials could impact the stability, permeability, and deformation of the layers, which is crucial for construction projects as well as the technical properties for industrial applications.

GEOLOGICAL SETTING

The Neogene clay materials that are the subject of this study are located in the area between the villages of Rakovitsa, Golemanovo, Staropatitsa and Bela, Northwest Bulgaria (Fig. 1). The study area is situated in the Kula tectonic zone, which is located near the westernmost part of the Moesian Platform (Tzankov, 1972, 1974; Ivanov, 1998; Dabovski

Fig. 1. a) Location map; b) Geological representation of the studied area based on the geological maps in scales 1:50 000 (map sheets Rakovitsa, Dimovo, Belogradchik; after Angelov *et al.*, 2006a–c) and 1:100 000 (map sheet Zaechar and Bor – after Decheva *et al.*, 1990; map sheet Vidin – Filipov *et al.*, 1992; map sheet Belogradchik – Angelov *et al.*, 1995).

and Zagorchev, 2009). The sedimentary cover of the Kula Zone consists of Jurassic, Cretaceous and Paleogene rock complexes. The Neogene–Quaternary sediments in this part of the Kula Zone lie normally over the older sediments and have the character of post-tectonic deposits (Angelov *et al.*, 2008).

The studied clay materials were collected from the Rakevo wedge of the Krivodol Formation, in the lower part of the lithological sequence (Kojumdgieva and Popov, 1988; Fig. 1b). The lithological, biostratigraphic, and sedimentological characteristics of the Sarmatian sediments of the Krivodol Formation have been studied in detail in the past and presented in the works of Kojumdgieva (1961), Popov *et al.* (1964), Kojumdgieva *et al.* (1978), Kojumdgieva and Popov (1966, 1988), Koleva-Rekalova (2000), etc. The Krivodol Formation consists mainly of clays and siltstones with intercalations of sands. The sediments of the Rakevo wedge are widespread in the area between the villages of Rakovitsa and Staropatitsa. The lower boundary of the wedge is transgressive and discordant with the intensively folded sediments of the Kula and Staropatitsa formations and is normally covered by the sediments of the Dimovo Formation. At its base, the Rakevo wedge is made up of clays, which alternate upwards with interlayers of silty clays and clayey sands. The sediments of the wedge were determined as late Volynian based on the represented fauna (Kojumdgieva and Popov, 1988).

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Mineralogical analysis was carried out at the Laboratory of X-Ray Structural Analysis of Sofia University “St. Kliment Ohridski”, Bulgaria. The phase composition of seven samples (three located in an area of 20 m² at the sampling points in Bela and four in the Staropatitsa area) and three samples from the clay fraction was determined by powder X-ray diffraction (XRD). The powder XRD patterns were recorded on a Bruker D8 Advance diffractometer. Filtered Co-K α radiation was used in the range of 2 θ 4–80°, step 0.02° 2 θ , and exposure time per step 1.5 s. The Diffrac. Eva software was used for qualitative and semi-quantitative phase composition determination.

The chemical analysis of the selected clay materials was performed by testing four samples from two sites – Bela (B-1) and Staropatitsa (ST-1, ST-2F, and ST-2M). Three of the samples are fresh and one of them (ST-2M) is matured. The location of the taken samples is indicated in Fig. 1. The chemical

characterization consisted of determining the major element concentrations by ICP-AES (Inductively Coupled Plasma Atomic Emission Spectroscopy) analysis on a Varian Vista-MPX spectrometer carried out at the Laboratory Test Center (LTC) of Kaolin Jsc., Bulgaria. The predominance of oxides was determined by using the triangular diagram of SiO₂–Al₂O₃–Fe₂O₃. The evaluation of the level of chemical alterations of the analyzed clay materials was carried out by calculation of CIA, following the formula:

$$\text{CIA} = (\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3 / (\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3 + \text{CaO} + \text{Na}_2\text{O} + \text{K}_2\text{O})) \times 100.$$

Materials with values between 5% and 60% are weakly altered, those with values between 60% and 80% are moderately altered, and materials with values >80% are highly altered. The obtained results were compiled in a ternary diagram of the evaluation of CIA (Nesbitt and Young, 1984).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Mineralogical composition

The obtained phase composition of representative clay samples from the two sampling sites is mainly represented by quartz, montmorillonite, and kaolinite and in lesser amounts mica, chlorite, and potassium feldspars (Fig. 2a, b). The composition and quantitative relationships of minerals in the Bela samples are almost constant and vary within 3–4 wt.%, which is within the error of method determination. The determined semi-quantitative contents of minerals to 100% from the crystal phase are quartz (55–57%), smectites (13–15%), kaolinites (19–21%), chlorite (7–8%), potassium feldspars (3–5%), and muscovite (2–3%).

In the composition of the samples from Staropatitsa, a greater range of quantitative relationships (in wt.%) is observed, mainly because of the strong variation in quartz content: quartz (55–75%), smectites (7–10%), kaolinites (13–21%), chlorite (0–8%), potassium feldspars (2–3%), and muscovite (3–9%), in accordance with the observed weak external inhomogeneity of the samples. A significant presence of goethite was found in the samples in which reddish-colored areas were observed (Fig. 2c).

The main clay minerals in both sites are represented by the two structural groups – smectite and kaolinite types, which make up more than 90–95% of the clay fraction (Fig. 2d). From the smectite minerals, montmorillonite and nontronite are recorded,

Fig. 2. Powder XRD patterns of: a) Bela sample; b) Staropatitsa sample; c) Staropatitsa sample with reddish coloring of some spots; d) clay fraction. Abbreviations: Q – quartz, Mtm – montmorillonite, Nont – nontronite, Kaol – kaolinite, Hal – halloysite, KFs – potassium feldspar, Ms – muscovite, and Goeth – goethite.

and from the kaolinite group, they are represented by kaolinite and halloysite.

Chemical composition

The results of the chemical analysis are shown in Table 1 as mass percentages of the oxides of the chosen samples from the two studied sites. The geochemical examination of clay materials could provide information about their technical qualities, as well as a detailed understanding of their origin (Crook, 1974). The investigated clay materials are composed mostly of silica (SiO_2), alumina (Al_2O_3), and iron oxide (Fe_2O_3), with minor amounts of TiO_2 , CaO, MgO, Na_2O , and K_2O . The Bela sample (B-1) contains 60.5% silica, 23.28% alumina, and 3.65% iron oxide. The Staropatitsa samples (ST-1, ST-2F, and ST-2M) had silica ranging from 54.30% to 65.70%, alumina ranging from 18.22% to 25.16%,

and iron oxide ranging from 3.50% to 4.16%. The presence of CaO, MgO, Na_2O , and P_2O_5 is also observed.

The high proportion of SiO_2 in the samples reveals the prevalence of quartz. The presence of kaolinite and other aluminum silicates explains the high Al_2O_3 concentration. The reported slightly elevated amount of Fe_2O_3 could be attributed to the presence of nontronite and chlorite. The higher Fe_2O_3 concentration in the reddish coloring of some spots is due to the presence of goethite. The proportion of K_2O and TiO_2 depends on the amount of illite/mica and anatase, and the presence of montmorillonite minerals could explain the MgO concentration in the samples. The geochemical composition correlates with the mineralogical data and indicates the existence of the distinct mineral phases that have crystallized as quartz and kaolinite/halloysite, according to the findings of this study.

Table 1
Chemical composition (wt. %) of the studied clay materials. LOI (loss on ignition) – weight loss of the sample after thermal heating at 1000 °C

Component wt. %	Sample			
	Bela	Staropatitsa		
	B-1	ST-1	ST-2F	ST-2M
SiO ₂	60.50	65.50	65.70	54.30
Al ₂ O ₃	23.28	19.15	18.22	25.16
Fe ₂ O ₃	3.65	3.50	3.66	4.16
TiO ₂	0.76	1.09	1.05	1.50
CaO	0.76	1.15	1.55	2.13
MgO	1.01	0.63	0.61	0.61
K ₂ O	1.63	1.28	1.22	1.64
Na ₂ O	0.20	0.22	0.22	0.34
P ₂ O ₅	0.087	0.021	0.021	0.043
LOI	7.83	7.20	7.38	9.82
Total	99.71	99.74	99.69	99.74
SiO ₂ /Al ₂ O ₃	2.59	3.42	3.60	2.15
CIA	89.98	87.84	85.90	85.95

The SiO₂/Al₂O₃ ratio shows little variation between the Bela and Staropatitsa samples (Table 1). A triangular diagram of SiO₂–Al₂O₃–Fe₂O₃ (Fig. 3) represents that all samples were placed towards the SiO₂ pole and along the SiO₂–Al₂O₃ axis, which coincides with a SiO₂/Al₂O₃ ratio. This demonstrates excesses of SiO₂ and Al₂O₃ and validates the existence of quartz and kaolinite in the analyzed samples. The low SiO₂/Al₂O₃ ratios in the material that are close to 2 indicate the presence of minerals of the kaolinite family (Tsozue *et al.*, 2017), whereas

higher values could indicate chemical maturity of the materials, the presence of free forms of silica, and/or clay minerals of type 2:1 such as montmorillonite. The proportions of type 1:1 clay minerals in the research samples were significantly higher than those of type 2:1.

CIA ranges from 85.90% to 89.98% (Fig. 4), indicating that the clay materials were subjected to significant alteration, which might be explained by morphological and climate conditions in the shallow basin where these materials were deposited.

Fig. 3. Position of clay materials in the triangular diagram SiO₂–Al₂O₃–Fe₂O₃.

Fig. 4. Position of the studied clay materials in the ternary diagram of Nesbitt and Young (1984).

Formation of the clay materials

The formation of clay materials involves complex processes influenced by various factors, such as climate, geology, and the duration and intensity of weathering or alteration events. Kaolinite is primarily formed through weathering and leaching of alumina-rich silicate minerals, such as feldspars, micas, and volcanic rocks. The leaching process removes soluble elements, leaving behind residual kaolinite. The primary formation of halloysite occurs through weathering of aluminosilicate minerals, such as feldspars and volcanic glass. Kaolinite and halloysite can also form through secondary alteration processes involving the interaction of existing minerals with hydrothermal fluids or groundwater. Under certain geological conditions, such as burial and diagenesis, kaolinite can form from the alteration of other clay minerals, such as smectite or illite, through chemical reactions and recrystallization.

In general, in regard to the clay materials' genesis in the study area, the deposition was performed at the end of the Neogene, when started the deposition of clayey sand complexes with different thicknesses which contain the studied materials. The clayey sediments were formed by the destruction and weathering of the acidic granitic massifs located in the southern margin of the basin – the Belogradchik pluton (Chunев *et al.*, 1962; Haydurov *et al.*, 1995), which has a high content of K- and Na-feldspars. The structural characteristics of the area predestine the presence and formation of transport channels like river valleys (*e.g.*, Agalareva, 2012) and other negative forms in which the weathered material could be transported and deposited and, after lithification, formed the plastic clay materials. The whole processes of formation and the source area need to be further investigated in detail because, although it is beyond the extent of this study, fault disintegration and weathering of the located to the south granite massif is one of the possibilities for the formation of the studied materials.

CONCLUSIONS

The phase composition of samples from Bela and Staropatitsa is mostly quartz and clay minerals, with minor quantities of mica, chlorite, and potassium feldspars. The mineral composition and quantitative relationships are mostly stable, but the Staropatitsa samples exhibit a wider variety of quantitative correlations owing to considerable

quartz content variation, weak external inhomogeneity, and the presence of goethite. Clay minerals are mainly from the smectite (montmorillonite and nontronite) and kaolinite (kaolinite and halloysite) groups, accounting for more than 90–95% of the clay fraction.

The chemical analysis indicated that silica and alumina were predominant in the analyzed samples (54.30–65.70% SiO₂; and 18.22–25.16% Al₂O₃), with medium contents of iron oxides. These results agree with the mineralogical analysis and the content of quartz, kaolinite/halloysite, which are confirmed also by the SiO₂/Al₂O₃ ratio. The percentage of MgO, K₂O, and TiO₂ content is explained by the presence of montmorillonite minerals, illite/mica, and anatase. The high values of the Chemical Index of Alteration show that clay materials underwent intense alteration.

Kaolinite and halloysite are clay minerals that have gained considerable attention in various scientific and industrial fields due to their unique properties and versatile uses. One of the possible industrial applications of the studied clay materials is in ceramic industry not only because of their mineralogical and chemical properties, which are suitable for this type of production, but also because of their light color (in most of the samples), high plasticity, and the low sand content. Moreover, the chemical and mineralogical properties of kaolinite and halloysite influence their behavior and interactions with the environment, and understanding their properties could provide valuable information for assessing the stability, permeability, and deformation properties of rock layers.

In conclusion, further investigation of the chemical and mineralogical characteristics, and technical parameters (like effective cohesion and plasticity) of these clay materials is essential for unraveling their formation processes, optimizing their industrial applications, assessing their environmental implications, and enhancing geologic and geotechnical assessments. The knowledge gained from these studies contributes to a deeper understanding of these clay materials and opens new avenues for their sustainable utilization in various fields.

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